

CONFLICT MANAGEMENT AND INTERNAL CONTROL AS PREDICTORS OF QUALITY OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE OF POLICE OFFICERS

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Conflict Management and Internal Control as Predictors of Quality of Work-Life Balance of Police Officers

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine which domain in conflict management and internal control significantly predicts the quality of work-life of police officers. Quantitative research utilizing a descriptive correlation survey was used in this study. Among the 178 total population, 123 police officers from the South Cotabato Police Provincial office were considered as respondents of this study using Slovin's formula. Adopted questionnaires were modified and used to gather the data. Considering this study is a descriptive correlational survey, Mean, Pearson R, and regression analysis were employed to treat the gathered data. This reveals that the conflict management level is high. The level of police internal control is high. At the same time, the quality of work-life for the police is high. Further, there was a significant relationship between conflict management and quality of work-life, internal control, and quality of work-life. The best domain that significantly predicts the quality of work-life of police officers in conflict management is applying a conflict management approach. In contrast, in terms of internal control, cash control is the best domain that significantly predicts the quality of work life.

Keywords: *criminal justice education, conflict management, internal control, quality of work-life, police officers*

Introduction

Work is an integral part of our daily life since it provides us with a living. We spend twelve hours a day at work, which accounts for one-third of our life. Quality work of life characterizes a person's overall experience linked to their profession. Police officers are under tremendous stress because doing a wide range of tasks are expected of them. Their tasks are routine work, investigations, movements of vital individuals, and confronting terrorists. A study noted that, on average, these employees work longer days than the minimum of 12 hours that they are required to work. Also, police officers do not attend large-scale events or receive annual holidays because they are needed even more during festivals. Daily routine tasks of police officers cause a great deal of stress (Pradhan, 2021).

Furthermore, work-life balance (WLB) reduces stress, job commitment, and satisfaction. Workplace stress is the reason for the need for improvements in the quality of work-life balance, and job stress, job commitment, and job satisfaction are all impacted by training and development. Furthermore, a higher quality of work-life balance raises employee satisfaction, which improves organizational productivity. Workers are content with the company's working conditions. Promotion and a participatory decision-making approach motivate most employees (Aruldoss et al., 2022; Patel, 2019).

Further, every institution needs organizational effectiveness, encompassing client and customer satisfaction and work-life balance. Organizational conflict management has become inevitable due to employee competition for scarce resources, authority, status, and recognition. Although conflicts do not necessarily reflect poorly on the organization, they can foster healthy rivalry, increase teamwork, and improve communication (John-Eke & Akintokunbo, 2020).

In addition, conflict management significantly affects the quality of life at work. It demonstrates that workers with more experience in conflict management have lower-quality work lives. Also, internal control significantly and favorably impacts the organizations and the quality of work-life balance. Organizational performance is positively and significantly impacted by the overall quality of work-life (Rahman et al., 2020; Sanjaya & Mayola, 2019).

Employee commitment, work quality, and internal control have significant effects on how well employees perform. Also, the performance of employees is significantly impacted simultaneously by internal control, work quality, and employee commitment. Additionally, a study found out that work commitments, supervision, and quality of work life have significant effect to the performance of workers (Hadi, 2021).

Even though, researchers have studied several factors affecting police officers' work-life balance, few studies have been conducted about how conflict management and internal control function as indicators of this crucial result. Although, conflict is being studied in law enforcement, studies on how good conflict management techniques can improve police officers' work-life balance is untypical. In the same way, the influence of internal control—an organizational term for the procedures and practices meant to guarantee accountability and compliance—on work-life balance has not received enough attention in the context of law enforcement. Thus, conducting a study on how conflict management and internal control predict the work-life balance among police officers is necessary.

Given the potential consequences for law enforcement personnel's performance and well-being, it is imperative to comprehend the predictors of police officers' work-life balance. Consequently, police officers frequently deal with high-stress levels, lengthy workdays, and challenging job duties which have a detrimental effect on their personal lives and level of job satisfaction. Thus, the study can provide important insights into organizational practices and strategies that can improve work-life balance in law enforcement agencies by looking at internal control and conflict management as predictors. Also, this study is of vital importance because it can provide

evidence to support evidence-based policies and interventions that aim to enhance police officer retention and well-being, which will ultimately result in more efficient and long-lasting law enforcement procedures.

Hence, to identify factors, conclude, and present recommendations, the researcher is determined in identifying the relationship among conflict management and internal control and the quality of work-life for police officers. This conclusion raises concerns for the intended beneficiaries of the study. This topic would be beneficial in understanding internal control, conflict management, and the quality of work-life of police officers. It makes use of the chance to address the desire for additional criminological research. As for the preceding factors, studies were not yet conducted particularly those about Koronadal City and the Philippines.

This study aimed to provide sufficient proof to an increasing body of data and to determine the significant effect of conflict management and internal control to the quality of work-life to improve the police learning process.

Research Objectives

Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. To describe the level of conflict management of police officers in terms of:
 - 1.1. understand the natural response to conflict;
 - 1.2. understand the context of the conflict; and
 - 1.3. apply a conflict management approach.
2. To ascertain the extent of workplace spirituality of public-school teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1. control environment;
 - 2.2. general operating control;
 - 2.3. cash controls
 - 2.4. expenditure controls;
 - 2.5. payroll; and
 - 2.6. information technology.
3. To determine the level of quality of work-life of police officers in terms of:
 - 3.1. work environment;
 - 3.2. organization culture and climate;
 - 3.3. relation and co-operation;
 - 3.4. training and development;
 - 3.5. compensation and rewards;
 - 3.6. facilities;
 - 3.7. job satisfaction and job security;
 - 3.8. autonomy of work; and
 - 3.9. adequacy of resources.
4. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. conflict management and quality of work-life; and
 - 4.2. internal control and quality of work-life.
5. To ascertain which domain in conflict management and internal control significantly predicts the quality of work-life.

Methodology

This study used a quantitative non-experimental research design using correlational techniques to identify the relationship between the degree of conflict management, internal control, and quality of work-life of the police officers in the South Cotabato Police Provincial Office. The systematic investigation of events by gathering numerical data and utilizing computational, mathematical, or statistical methods is known as quantitative research. The positivist paradigm, which supports statistical breakdown techniques like inferential statistics, hypothesis testing, mathematical exposition, randomization in experimental and quasi-experimental designs, blinding, structured protocols, and questionnaires with a limited range of prearranged answers, is the foundation of quantitative research (Adedoyin, 2020).

According to Indu and Vidhukumar (2019), non-experimental study designs describe existing phenomena without adjusting study conditions to influence subjects' responses or changing an independent variable and examining the state of something currently and how it used to be. One of the broad categories of research designs is non-experimental, which does not introduce external variables, and the researcher observes the phenomena as they occur naturally. This research design does not intentionally manipulate variables or control the setting. Further, the correlation coefficient is a statistical measure frequently utilized in studies to examine or demonstrate the agreement between two methods or variables. It will examine not just the fundamentals of the correlation coefficient, such as its assumptions and interpretation, but also essential restrictions when utilizing the correlation coefficient, including its sensitivity to the range of observations and its assumption of a linear relationship (Janse et al., 2021).

Moreover, measuring the relationship between two variables is a part of correlational research. Attitudes and behaviors are examples

of variables. A potential variable is anything measurable. The fundamental feature of correlational research is that all participants provide scores on the same two variables; participants do not perform one task while others complete another. Rather than focusing on an individual's score, correlational research aims to comprehend the relationship between two variables in a larger sample of participants. Researchers look for a sample representative of the relevant population (Walters, 2020).

Additionally, correlational research design examines relationships between variables without requiring any control or manipulation from the researcher. Correlation reflects the direction and strength of the relationship between two or more variables. A correlation may have a positive or negative direction. Correlational research is the best option when collecting data from natural environments. The application of correlation research is externally valid to real-world scenarios (Bhandari, 2021). The locale of this study was at the South Cotabato Police Provincial Office. General Orders #116 activated the South Cotabato Constabulary/Integrated National Police Command IV PC Zone Headquarters, Camp Evangelista, Cagayan de Oro City, dated January 5, 1968, stationed in Koronadal, South Cotabato. On December 15, 2017, PSSUPT Franklin A Alvero inaugurated the new site of the Police Provincial Office situated at Brgy. Morales, Koronadal City. The order materialized the transfer of different offices of SCPPO to the new building in January 2018.

A portion of the empire province of Cotabato, a former American colony founded by Governor General Francis Burton Harrison but ceded to the Republic of the Philippines on July 4, 1946, was transferred to the newly formed Province of South Cotabato on July 14, 1967, according to Republic Act 4849. Situated strategically in the southernmost region of Mindanao's mainland, it is bordered to the south by the Celebes Sea, to the north by Maguindanao, and the east by Davao del Sur and Sultan Kudarat in the West (South Cotabato Police Provincial Office [SCPPO] Clear book, 2022).

The study's respondents were 123 police officers from the South Cotabato Police Provincial Office. The study used simple random sampling to collect objective and allowable data. Using this sampling technique, everyone in the population had an equal chance of being chosen. Simple random sampling is the easiest to understand among the probability sampling techniques because it only requires one random selection and minimal prior population knowledge. Any research done on this sample should have high internal and external validity and be less susceptible to research biases like selection and sampling bias because it uses randomization. This study utilized simple random sampling to draw statistical conclusions about a population. Randomization is the best way to lessen the impact of potential confounding variables. Randomization also helps to ensure high internal validity. Additionally, a simple random sample has high external validity when the sample size is large enough because it accurately captures the features of the larger population (Thomas, 2020). The researcher used Slovin's equation for the sample population by calculating the number of police officers whose total population size in the South Cotabato Police Provincial Office is 178 with an allowable error of 0.05 percent.

Inclusion criteria included male and female police officers who are commissioned and noncommissioned, with a rank of patrolman/patrol woman to Police Colonel assigned in 14 offices of the South Cotabato Police Provincial Office. This study also included police officers who wrote on the consent form and survey instrument, understand instructions, and those who willfully submitted to the test. Additionally, those who were willing to consent, and finally, those who were willing to participate, were all included in the study.

Meanwhile, exclusion criteria included the following: police officers having a rank of Police Brigadier General to Police General, police officers not assigned at the South Cotabato Police Provincial Office, utility personnel, non-uniformed personnel, and individuals unwilling to become participants. Lastly, withdrawal criteria included the researcher's violation of the respondent's request for secrecy and privacy in their identification. That there were no penalties or benefits to which respondents were otherwise obligated and that respondents were free to decide not to engage, refuse to participate, or end engagement at any time. It also included how any discomfort or negative impacts, such as any cognitive risks, were defined or clarified, how likely they were to reduce these risks, and any necessary next steps.

Validity and Reliability of the Questionnaire

The survey questionnaire for conflict management was adapted and modified from the study of Gaumer Erickson et al. (2018). The conflict management checklist had the following indicators: understanding the nature of the response to conflict, understanding the context of the conflict, and applying a conflict management approach. The study used the following array of means and their definitions to determine the level of conflict management among police officers.

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	This means that the conflict management of police is observed at all times.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that the conflict management of police is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that the conflict management of police is occasionally observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means that the conflict management of police is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that the conflict management of police is not observed at all.

The study adapted and modified the internal control questionnaire from Sadu (2017) to fit the study and subject to the experts' validation. The internal control questionnaire has the following indicators: control environment, general operating control, cash controls, expenditure controls, payroll, and information technology. This study used the following array of means with its definition for internal control of the police officers.

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	This means that the internal control of police is observed at all times.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that the internal control of police is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that the internal control of police is occasionally observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means that the internal control of police is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that the internal control of police is not observed at all.

This study adopted and modified the survey questionnaire on the quality of work-life from the study of Swamy et al. (2015). The quality of work-life checklist includes the following indicators: work environment, organizational culture and climate, relations and cooperation, training and development, compensation and rewards, facilities, job satisfaction and job security, autonomy of work, and adequacy of resources. The table below shows the five orderable degrees of their respective ranges, means, and descriptions used in assessing the quality of work-life of police officers.

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	This means that the police quality of work-life is manifested at all times.
3.40 – 4.19	High	This means that the police quality of work-life is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that the police quality of work-life is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	This means that the police quality of work-life is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that the police quality of work-life is never manifested at all.

The researcher applied to the RMMC ERC to conduct the study and had it signed by the Graduate School Dean. Then, the researcher requested permission from the Provincial Director to collect the data. Immediately after the Provincial Director's approval, the researcher endorsed the Provincial Director's letter to the Section Chief of the South Cotabato Police Provincial Office requesting permission to gather data. The researcher followed the exact process based on the study of Dingman (2020), in which the researcher sent a letter containing the study's objectives, potential participants' roles, and how data would be shared and utilized. After obtaining permission from the department heads, the researcher secured a list of prospective participants from the respective human resources divisions. Also, the researcher asked the participants a series of screening questions before forwarding to the survey questionnaire. The researchers directed the qualified participants to the survey questionnaire (Dingman, 2020). At this point, the researcher had managed and transmitted the survey to the poll through and through. The Administration section has issued a Certificate of Appearance for documentation purposes.

Hence, the researcher gathered, tallied, and classified all the data from the respondents using different scales. The researcher also broke down and translated the measurable after-effects of the information with the assistance of the statistician. The statistician also reached a determination and planned suggestions given the reason for the study.

The study used the following statistical tools in the treatment/computation of data tested at a 0.05 level of significance: Mean. This tool determined the level of conflict management, internal control, and quality of work-life of police officers to answer objectives 1, 2, and 3. Pearson R. This determined the significant relationship between the level of conflict management, internal control, and quality of work-life of police officers in answer to objective 4. Regression Analysis. This statistical tool determined that the domain in conflict management and internal control significantly predicts the quality of work-life of South Cotabato Police Provincial Office in answer to objective 5

Results and Discussion

Level of Conflict Management

The first objective of this study was to describe the level of police conflict management based on the evaluation of police personnel. The study also described the level of police conflict management in terms of understanding the natural response to conflict, understanding the context of the conflict, and applying a conflict management approach.

Presented in Table 1 are the data on the level of police conflict management. The level of police conflict management reaches the overall mean of 3.91, which indicates high. The result revealed that in the PNP organization, police conflict management is often observed and requires development and improvement for effective conflict resolution. From this data, understanding natural response to conflict has a total mean score of 3.91 with a descriptive level of high. The result signified that the PNP personnel often observed conflict management. The indicator of understanding the context of the conflict also has a total mean of 3.91 with a high a high descriptive level, which means that PNP personnel often observe conflict management. On the indicator of applying a conflict management approach, the total mean is 3.91, which is high. The result showed that the PNP personnel often observed conflict management.

The analyzed data communicated that conflict management in three indicators—understanding the natural response to conflict, understanding the context of the conflict, and applying a conflict management approach—garnered a high descriptive level. The result indicated that police personnel often observed conflict management. The finding demonstrated that effective conflict resolution methods can significantly enhance the quality of decisions. Effective conflict-resolution management techniques increase good communication, time management, teamwork, and organizational productivity. A high level of organizational performance will accomplish the organization's goals and objectives. If the company is able to resolve disputes within its operations in a way that is both effective and efficient (Omene, 2021).

In addition, this finding also aligned with the fact that executive or organizational conflict management is very effective at resolving conflicts when they arise. However, it is not enough to address staff expectations for conflict resolution. Furthermore, preparation for the collaborative process, communication, trust-building, empowerment, and collaborative leadership are crucial to successfully applying conflict management in these circumstances. However, this finding disagreed that a moderate amount of the police officers' conflict management techniques involved compromise for conceptual conflicts, competition for contentious situations, and conflicts of interest (Almeida et al., 2018; Galman et al., 2021; Rahmat et al., 2020).

In addition, when dealing with cases of conflict, police officers need to be able to maintain composure, communicate, act appropriately, and listen intently to all sides involved. Police officers also need to be able to follow police procedures, negotiation principles, conflict analysis techniques, and management strategies by creating individualized work plans that will allow them to intervene, manage, and provide the appropriate resolution. The data coincided with the study on police officer's conflict management styles, which ranked high. For police officers, compromise is the most common style of conflict management. Compromising parties often use underlying problems to explain differences in negotiation and intervention processes. Police play many good roles in organizations and relationships (Adame et al., 2019; Agastra, 2018).

Table 1. *Level of Conflict Management*

Indicators	Mean	Description
1. Understand Natural Response to Conflict	3.91	High
2. Understand Context of the Conflict	3.91	High
3. Apply a Conflict Management Approach	3.91	High
Total/Average	3.91	High

Level of Internal Control

The study's second objective was to determine the level of police internal control. Control environment, general operating controls, cash controls, expenditure controls, payroll, and information technology are the measurements of the level of police internal control. Table 2 shows the data on the level of internal controls gauged by the respondents from their knowledge and experience. The level of internal control has an overall mean of 3.93, which means high. The result expressed that the police often observed the internal control in the PNP organization, which is needed to establish and upgrade to achieve greater internal control. From this information, cash controls have the highest mean score of 4.02 closely followed by general operating controls, with a mean of 3.99. General operating controls. Expenditure controls and payroll followed general operating control with a mean of 3.91. Also, information technology and control environment mean 3.89 and 3.88, respectively. All the indicators have a high descriptive level, with a mean range of 3.88 to 4.02, often observed in internal control.

Results explicitly exposed a high internal control regarding the control environment, general operating controls, cash controls, expenditure controls, payroll, and information technology. The result expressed that the police often observed the police's internal control. This finding also aligned with internal control, which refers to the policies, methods, and practices employed to attain organizational objectives. These objectives are ensuring operational efficiency, safeguarding assets, and adherence to rules and regulations. The findings imply that humans designed, operated, and monitored the inherent limitations of internal control. It supported the study of internal control to ascertain the operations of individual police units and whether those units were accomplishing the objectives established at the organizational level (Lawal, 2019; Lobnikar & Ropoša, 2020).

Also, this finding agreed that Internal control is a unique activity that includes tracking results and comparing them to predetermined

targets on an ongoing basis. Generally, control refers to the observation and assessment of the accomplished outcome. Internal police control is a type of self-control that police officers exercise within their ranks. Combating crime and corruption within the police force is the primary objective of the internal control unit. In addition, the policing system's internal control has evolved and is changing quickly (Vuković, 2021).

In addition, this study discussed the relationship between the government's control over police powers and the new demands made by citizens at the home, neighborhood, and community levels. Ethical standards are presented in the conclusions to manage police effectively and efficiently. Furthermore, this finding concurred that internal controls is produced when workers believe their agencies have a higher level of organizational justice are more successful at dealing with workplace misconduct (Fridell et al., 2021; Lambert, 2023).

Table 2. *Level of Internal Control*

Indicators	Mean	Description
1. Control Environment	3.88	High
2. General Operating Controls	3.99	High
3. Cash Controls	4.02	High
4. Expenditure Controls	3.91	High
5. Payroll	3.91	High
6. Information Technology	3.89	High
Total/Average	3.93	High

Level of Quality of Work of life

The third objective of this study was to assess the level of police quality of work-life. The study also measured the police quality of work-life in terms of work environment, organization culture and climate, relation and cooperation, training and development, compensation and rewards, facilities, job satisfaction and job security, autonomy of work, and adequacy of resources. Shown in Table 3 are the data on the level of police quality of work-life while they view their satisfaction and contentedness as a police officer. The police quality of work-life has an overall mean of 3.86, which is high.

The police often manifest the quality of work-life based on the result. Data shows that the work environment has the highest mean score of 4.02 with a high descriptive level. The result attested that the police often manifest the quality of work-life balance. In addition, relation and cooperation have the second highest mean score of 3.93 with a high description level, which means that the police often manifest the quality of work-life. Subsequently, organization culture and climate have a mean score of 3.92, which means that the police often manifest the quality of their work-life balance. Facilities have a mean score of 3.92 with a description of high, which means the police often manifest the quality of work-life balance. Also, job satisfaction and job security have a mean score of 3.91 with a high descriptive level, which means that the police often manifest the quality of work life. Compensation and rewards followed job satisfaction and job security with a mean of 3.87, which means high. The result indicated that the police often manifest the quality of work-life balance. The autonomy of work has a mean score of 3.84 with a description of high, which means the police often manifest the quality of work-life. Also, training and development have a mean score of 3.77, which is high, and the police often manifest the quality of their work-life balance. Furthermore, adequacy of resources had the lowest mean score of 3.6, which means high, and the police often manifest the quality of work-life.

It was revealed in the data that there is a high Quality of Work-life in all indicators in terms of work environment, organization culture and climate, relation and cooperation, training and development, compensation and rewards, facilities, job satisfaction and job security, autonomy of work and adequacy of resources. The result expresses that the police often manifest the quality of work-life. A study reinforced the findings on that employee happiness and discontent, administrative concerns about effective production, social balance, and integrity should consider quality of work life that includes work ethics, different aspects of the working environment, safety precautions. Further, the result supported the study on quality of work life that to improve police well-being, the policymakers and management must take immediate action to address the high quality of work life (QWL) dimensions that fall under dominant ill-being (Patel, 2019; Yadav et al., 2022).

Furthermore, the study's findings supported that police officers have a moderate quality of work-life. Therefore, more attention should be given to recognizing the influential factors to create the necessary modifications to enhance the police Quality of Work-life. Moreover, the study found that the type of management and leadership, the availability of supportive and rest areas, and the extent to which employees accept their working conditions impact the police officer's quality of work-life. The authorities have to enhance the work-life balance of the police personnel so that they take pleasure in their jobs and organization. Thus, the process by which the company acknowledges its accountability for both employee skills and superior organizational performance is what determines the quality of work life (Parida & Sundaray, 2019; Tabanejad et al., 2021).

Furthermore, employee satisfaction in the workplace is high, which is viewed as a competitive advantage because dedicated employees are responsible for improvements in customer service and product quality. Improving the quality of work life at work is mostly dependent on the workplace. The feeling of being respected as individuals and professionals while being integrated into a good work environment influences the perception of positively impacting organizational performance. In addition, the primary demographic traits that cast a negative light on the quality of work life are low income, the need for education, the predominance of contract workers, and the concentration of youth with less experience (Bala & Sharma, 2021; Leitão et al., 2019).

Table 3. Level of Quality of Work of Life

Indicators	Mean	Description
1. Work environment	4.02	High
2. Organization Culture And Climate	3.92	High
3. Relation and Co-operation	3.93	High
4. Training and Development	3.77	High
5. Compensation and Rewards	3.87	High
6. Facilities	3.92	High
7. Job satisfaction and Job Security	3.91	High
8. Autonomy of Work	3.84	High
9. Adequacy of Resources	3.60	High
Total/Average	3.86	High

Significance of the Relationship between Conflict Management and Quality of Work-life

The very crucial purpose of this study was to seek a significant relationship between conflict management and the quality of work-life of police officers. Table 4 presents the computation figures tested at the Alpha level of 0.05. The overall t-value on the correlation between conflict management and quality of work-life was 0.147 less than the computed value of c-value 0.605 with a degree of freedom of 198. Since the t-value or tabular value is less than the computed value, there is a significant relationship between conflict management and the quality of work-life of police officers. Therefore, the study rejects the null hypothesis.

There were various possible reasons for a significant relationship between conflict management and quality of work-life exposed in the data presented. According to the study, one of the key elements that influences life quality is conflict. Institutions should avoid these elements before conflict arises to prevent issues from arising even after conflict has begun. The study of every institution needs organizational effectiveness, which encompasses client and customer satisfaction, and work-life balance. Conflict management has become inevitable due to employee competition for scarce resources, authority, status, and recognition. Conflicts do not reflect poorly on the organization, as always. When handled well, they can foster healthy competition, increase teamwork, and improve communication (John-Eke & Akintokunbo, 2020; Karakaş & Tezcan, 2019).

Table 4. Significant Relationship between Conflict Management and Quality of Work Life

Variables	Df	r _{xy} value		Decision	Analysis
		n=200			
		Computed	Tabular	a= 0.05	
Conflict Management	198	0.605	0.147	Reject null hypothesis	There is a significant relationship.
Quality of Work of Life					

Significance of the Relationship between Internal Control and Quality of Work-life

Determining the significant relationship between internal control and the quality of work-life of police officers is one of the study's aims. Figures of computation were presented in Table 5 and tested at the Alpha level of 0.05. The overall computed value on the correlation between internal control and the c-value of quality of work-life is 0.674, which is greater than the tabular value t-value of 0.147 with a degree of freedom of 198. Since the c-value, or computed value, is greater than the t-value or tabular value, there is a significant relationship between internal control and the quality of work-life of police officers, which results in rejecting the null hypothesis.

Further, manifested in Table 4 is the significant relationship between conflict management and the quality of work-life of police officers. Also, Table 5 shows the significant relationship between internal control and the quality of work-life of police officers. Since the domains of conflict management correlated with the overall quality of work-life of police officers, and internal control correlated with the overall quality of work-life of police officers, all showed significant relationships. The computed c-value is greater than the tabular t-value, which tested at the Alpha level of 0.05. Furthermore, when each study variable correlated with the overall quality of work-life, the result revealed that all study variables have a significant relationship with t-values less than the c-value.

Table 5. *Significant Relationship between Internal Control and Quality of Work of Life*

Variables	Df	r _{xy} value		Decision	Analysis
		n=200			
		Computed	Tabular	a= 0.05	
Internal					
Control	198	0.674	0.147	Reject null	There is a
Vs				hypothesis	significant
Quality of					relationship.
Work of Life					

Significance of the Influence of the Domain of Conflict Management, Internal Control on the Quality of Work-life

The result revealed that conflict management and internal control significantly predict the quality of work-life of police officers since the probability value is $p < 0.05$. $R^2 .486$. The result implied that 48.6% of the conflict management and internal control predict the quality of work-life of police officers while other factors influence the remaining 51.4%. Also, the result revealed that conflict management in terms of understanding the natural response to conflict, understanding the context of the conflict, and applying a conflict management approach have mean scores of 2.48, 1.021, and 3.480, respectively. Further, it revealed that the t-values of internal control in terms of control environment, general operating control, cash control, expenditure controls, payroll, and informal technology were 2.786, 1.45, 1.987, 3.76, and .974, respectively. Therefore, among the three indicators of conflict management, understanding the natural response to conflict and applying a conflict management approach predict the quality of work-life of police officers. In contrast, internal control, control environment, cash control, and payroll predict the quality of work-life of police officers with $p < 0.05$. The best domain that significantly predicts the quality of work-life of police officers in terms of conflict management applies a conflict management approach with a coefficient of .275 and $p = .004$, which is lesser than 0.05 significance level, while in terms of internal control, the best domain that significantly predicts the quality of work life is cash control with a coefficient of .256 and $p = .006$ which is lesser than 0.05 significance level.

Among the three indicators of conflict management, understanding the natural response to conflict and applying a conflict management approach predict significantly the quality of work-life of police officers. In contrast, internal control, control environment, cash control, and payroll significantly predict the quality of work-life of police officers. The best domain that significantly predicts the quality of work-life of police officers in conflict management is applying a conflict management approach. In contrast, the best domain that significantly predicts the quality of work life is cash control under internal control.

Table 6. *Domains of Conflict Management and Internal Control of Police Officers that Predicts Quality of Work-life*

Conflict Management	Quality of Work Life		
	B	t-value	p-value
Understand Natural Response to Conflict	.215	2.48	.004
Understand Context of the Conflict	.070	1.021	.309
Apply a Conflict Management Approach	.275	3.480	.001
Internal Control			
Control Environment	.214	2.786	.095
General Operating Control	.08	1.45	2.541
Cash Control	.256	1.987	.006
Expenditure Controls			
Payroll	.238	3.76	1.235
Informal Technology	.76	.974	1.005
R	.729		
R-square	.486		
F-value	102.13		
P-value	.000		

Conclusions

Based on the study, the following conclusions are derived: Overall, there was a high level of conflict management in three indicators: understanding the natural response to conflict, understanding the context of the conflict, and applying a conflict management approach. This means that the police often observe conflict management. In terms of the level of internal control, all indicators, which are control environment, general operating controls, cash controls, expenditure controls, payroll, and information technology, have a high level of conflict management, which means police often observe their internal control. Also, the level of quality of work-life was high in all indicators in terms of work environment, organization culture and climate, relation and cooperation, training and development, compensation and rewards, facilities, job satisfaction, and job security, the autonomy of work and adequacy of resources showing that the police often manifested the quality of work-life.

Furthermore, there was a significant relationship between conflict management and quality of work-life and internal control wherein conflict management and internal control have the best and most significant influence on the quality of work-life.

In addition, police officers' work-life quality is significantly predicted by conflict management and internal control, while other factors influence it for others. Therefore, among the three indicators of conflict management, understanding the natural response to conflict and applying a conflict management approach predicts the quality of work-life of police officers significantly. While in terms of internal control, control environment, cash control, and payroll significantly predict the quality of work-life of police officers. The best domain that significantly predicts the quality of work-life of police officers in conflict management is applying a conflict management approach. In contrast, cash control is the best domain that significantly predicts the quality of work life under internal control.

The researcher recommends the following for a better relationship among conflict management, internal control, and quality of work-life: First, Police Organizations may focus on providing comprehensive conflict management training to police officers all over the world, establishing clear policies, procedures, and protocols that promote accountability, transparency, and ethical conduct within police organizations since enhancing the quality of work life for police officers is essential for their well-being and job satisfaction. Second, Police officers may be trained in conflict management at the police provincial office level for more consciousness on peace, security, and interpersonal matters and empirical studies which are required to evaluate the police's readiness and competency in conflict management, monitoring of conflict management practices and the development of a written conflict management policy; address police agency needs evaluation in program implementation particular in the control environment. Third, the organization may plan strategic and transition management including implementation systems and information technology, Revitalized PNP Internal Cleansing, and Strategic Planning on the Moral Recovery Program of the PNP. The Philippine National Police may provide resources, training, and development, and work autonomy for police personnel that would help improve their quality of work life. Lastly, to enhance the adequacy of resources within the Philippine National Police organization by understanding resource requirements, organizations can make informed decisions regarding allocation and utilization.

Moreover, teachers may engage in practices that may enhance mindfulness and may help them experience positive emotions and a sense of connection to their work, may focus on developing their compassion, mindfulness, and sense of meaningful work to enhance their workplace spirituality, and may practice being fully engaged in their works and pay attention to their surroundings and actions.

Finally, this study may be a starting point for further research on professional commitment, job satisfaction, and workplace spirituality among public school teachers. Future research may explore additional variables, such as the role of leadership and organizational culture, and may also assess teacher's performance and student's outcomes.

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